

Gamification to Improve Writing Skills in B1 Level Students

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Abstract: The development of effective writing skills has long been a challenging endeavor, and educators and learners alike are constantly seeking innovative methods to improve writing proficiency. Gamification, the application of game elements and principles to non-game contexts, has emerged as a promising approach to address this educational challenge. The objective aids to explore the use of gamification in the context of enhancing writing skills, contributing to the language improvement and encouraging outcomes. Gamification in writing education leverages the inherent motivation that games offer, such as engagement, competition, and rewards, to create an enjoyable and effective learning experience. Through the incorporation of gamified elements, including points, badges, leaderboards, and narrative-driven challenges, students are encouraged to become more proactive and persistent in their writing practice. Furthermore, it addresses the impact of gamification on motivation, self-efficacy, and collaborative learning, providing insights into the potential benefits for learners. In conclusion, gamification presents a promising way to enrich writing education by making the learning process engaging, motivating, and enjoyable. Through a well-designed gamified approach, educators and learners can tap into the full potential of gamification to improve writing skills and foster a lifelong love for writing.

Key points: English language, Writing, Gamification, Second Language Learning, Motivational Theory, Student Engagement.

The pursuit for proficient writing skills has always been a demanding journey, and in today's fast-paced world, the need for effective communication through the written word is more critical than ever. Educators and learners alike continually seek innovative ways to improve writing proficiency, searching for methods that can engage and inspire while honing the craft of expression. In response to this ongoing educational challenge, the concept of gamification has emerged as a promising and invigorating approach. The present research aims to explore the use of gamification in the context of enhancing writing skills, contributing to the language improvement and encouraging outcomes.

In this concern, gamification, the integration of game elements and principles into non-gaming contexts, is not a new concept, but its application in enhancing writing skills has sparked a revolution in how we approach this fundamental aspect of education. In this dynamic fusion of education and entertainment, gamification leverages the inherent motivation that games offer, such as engagement, competition, and rewards, to create an enjoyable and effective learning experience.

In addition, this introduction sets the stage for an exploration of the captivating world of gamification and its transformative role in improving writing skills. It opens the door to a realm where points, badges, leaderboards, and narrative-driven challenges become tools that motivate students to become proactive, persistent, and skillful writers. The article uses a mix methodology that applies qualitative and quantitative approaches, with the support of a questionnaire to understand the student's perspective about gamification and writing skills. The objective aids to explore the use of gamification in the context of enhancing writing skills, contributing to the language improvement and encouraging outcomes. A main conclusion that emerges from the study is that the lack of training and technological resources affect the correct application of gamification in schools.

Pedagogical approaches

Pedagogical strategies for implementing gamification in education involve the intentional infusion of gaming elements and principles into the educational process, with the aim of increasing engagement, motivation, and the acquisition of knowledge and skills. In this sense, Hitchens, & Tulloch (2018) agree that students have fun and improve their learning through gamification.

A variety of educational methods can be applied to effectively integrate gamification into educational environments:

Integration of gaming mechanics

This approach centers on merging specific game components and mechanics like scoring, badges, leaderboards, and rewards into the educational context. These elements foster a sense of competition, accomplishment, and immediate feedback, thus encouraging active participation and the pursuit of improvement by students. From this perspective, Menon, & Romero (2020) coincide that game mechanics motivates the learners to participate actively in the challenges, as a consequence, the teaching learning process becomes more successful and enjoyable.

Narrative-driven learning

According to Wu, & Chen (2020), the power of storytelling can be harnessed as a potent pedagogical tool within gamification, since students are involved and increase their curiosity. In this method, educational content is presented as a story where students take on challenges and resolve problems within a captivating narrative. This technique immerses learners in a context that renders learning more engaging and pertinent.

Simulations

Simulations create a hands-on learning environment where students can apply theoretical knowledge to real-world situations. In this way, Foronda et al. (2020) claim that simulations are positive educational support because the students gain experience and develop problem-solving skills.

Collaborative gamification

This approach fosters collaboration among students by introducing cooperative gaming elements. In this concern, Sailer, & Homner (2020) stand out that collaborative activities, challenge students to work together in order to achieve a common objective, promoting teamwork and productive skills.

Role-playing

Learning can be enhanced through role-playing games (RPGs) by assigning students specific roles within a scenario. In this regard, Nazarov (2022) asserts that his approach stimulates critical thinking and decision-making, and motivates students to get involved in the development of the learning process.

Feedback and games

Effective feedback mechanisms are vital in gamification. Huang et al. (2019) claim that offering immediate and constructive feedback, learners can monitor their progress and recognize their strengths and areas for improvement, the authors also highlight that peer feedback supports the improvement of the students' knowledge and their interpersonal skills.

Competition and leaderboards

Friendly competition can serve as a motivating factor. Akhriza, & Mumpuni (2019) coincide that leaderboards display the progress and achievements of students, stimulating a desire to excel and outperform peers. It's also important to keep a balance between competition and a supportive, inclusive learning environment.

Gamified assessment

Santos Villalva et al. (2020) highlight that gamification should be integrated into assessment methods, providing students with opportunities to showcase their learning through creative and interactive means, which involves lots of motivational factors to fulfill successfully the tasks.

In conclusion, educators should carefully choose pedagogical approaches that align with their learning objectives and the requirements of their students. Effective gamification in education includes and relates elements of gaming design with a variety of pedagogical principles to create a motivating and engaging learning experience.

Writing skills

Developing writing skills is an effective communicative tool for improving English language. However, it is a skill that requires some time, strategies and creativity that matches the teachers' and students' needs inside and outside the classroom. In this regard, Eskalieva, & Jaksulikova (2021) recognize the importance of cultivating strong writing abilities. The authors highlight that proficient writing skills empower individuals to craft both formal and informal reports, script compelling presentations, and enhance creativity and communication.

This multifaceted process involves various stages, such as brainstorming, meticulous planning, mind mapping, drafting for smaller projects or extensive theses, obtaining feedback, and crafting narratives that range from brief anecdotes to extensive narratives. Furthermore, Muluneh (2018) suggests that achieving proficiency in writing paragraphs is a gradual process that necessitates time and experience. The author also recommends that a writer pays attention to the essential attributes of a paragraph, such as unity, coherence, and cohesion.

From another contribution, Zhang (2022) state the importance of developing enough vocabulary that permits learners to create and spell correctly their writing in single sentences or paragraphs. Moreover, Duran et al. (2019) coincide that educators should transition from conventional writing methods to more contemporary approaches, where students assume greater independence and become central figures in the classroom. Consequently, teachers should guide their students to collaborate in teams in a dynamic manner, fostering their active engagement and facilitating meaningful learning.

Gamification and writing skills

There are some games that should be considered to promote the improvement of writing skills. However, Kusumawarti, & Subiyantoro (2020) remark the importance of taking the students' learning styles into account, since it brings beneficial impact on the advancement of narrative writing.

From this point of view, Mazhar (2019) firmly believes that digital games highly contribute to increase motivation in students, make easy to develop classroom management, support cooperative learning, and propel the students' creativity and active participation. In addition, Castillo Cuesta (2022) mentions Genially games as a supportive tool that checks progress in terms of identifying correct grammar and vocabulary, structuring ideas, and displaying an understanding of essay structure. The author includes that the students can be able to display a favorable attitude towards the utilization of game-based activities, which further enhance their motivation and participation.

On the other hand, Ernawati et al. (2019) highlight the importance and meaningful outcomes that using card and picture games bring out to classrooms, since the learners are encouraged to develop their writing skills and feel motivated to participate actively in the teaching learning process. From another perspective, Yolanda, & Hadi (2019) assert that using puppets games can improve the development of speaking skills. However, it is important to include that those kind of games not only improve speaking skills but also writing skills when the teachers make their students to write the dialogues and scripts. In consequence, the students can be able to improve various language skills by using puppet games.

In the study conducted by Wijoyo (2021), it is emphasized that interviews not only provide an avenue for the application of diverse linguistic structures and vocabulary but also facilitate the cultivation of socio-emotional skills among English as a Foreign Language (EFL) students. This approach allows students to explore a range of language structures and vocabulary in a practical context while concurrently enhancing their ability to engage on a social and emotional level.

Methodology

The present article used a mix methodology that involved qualitative and quantitative approaches that supported the analysis of a questionnaire designed for 72 students who belong to 9th grade in a public high school located in the south of Quito, Ecuador. The questionnaire contained 10 questions that also were supported by a Likert scale with frequency items (Always, Usually, Sometimes and Never). In this sense, a statistical table was used to provide percentages of the results. It is important to highlight that there was permission from the school authorities to carry out the questionnaire, since the students' answers were anonymous and their names are not mentioned in the article or in the responses and analysis.

It can be observed that there is some lack of creativity and motivation from teachers, since the students do not feel enough encouraged to learn the English language by using games in class.

It is also important to highlight that the students prefer online or interactive games that use technology. However, a tremendous disadvantage is that most of the public schools and high schools do not have internet access or laboratories that support their modern learning.

It can be drawn that gamification, the use of game elements and principles in non-game contexts, has shown potential in improving various skills, including writing. However, there are challenges when it comes to implementing gamification effectively for enhancing writing skills.

Teachers should receive training on how to effectively integrate gamification into their writing instruction. This includes understanding the principles of gamification, selecting appropriate tools and games, and managing gamified activities within the curriculum.

Continuous research and evaluation are essential to measure the effectiveness of gamification in improving writing skills. This data can inform best practices and help educators make data-driven decisions about the use of gamification.

While gamification holds promise for improving writing skills, overcoming the lack of support requires a concerted effort from educators, institutions, and developers to ensure that the potential benefits of gamified writing instruction are fully realized.

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